

A novel synthesis of the north west portion of Lasonolide A – an anticancer macrolide using Claisen rearrangement

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A simplified analogue of Lasonolide A (C₂₃-C₃₅ side chain) was synthesized using Fujisawa's stereoselective variant of the Ireland Claisen ester rearrangement.

Lasonolide A (**1**) isolated from the shallow water Caribbean marine sponge *forcepia* sps by McConnel *et al.*, represents a new class of marine derived biologically active macrolide. It shows potent anticancer activity and cytotoxicity with a value of IC₅₀ of 40 and 20 µg/ml against A549 human lung carcinoma and P388 murine leukemia cell lines. Impressive biological activity coupled with structural complexity make this molecule a synthetic target of keen interest. It may be mentioned here that any total synthesis of this compound has not been reported so far.

We have earlier reported the synthesis of the C₁₈-C₂₃ tetrahydropyran ring moiety² and the stereoselective synthesis of the eastern C₇-C₁₆ segment of Lasonolide A³. In continuation of our work, we now report a model synthesis of the North Western C₂₃-C₃₅ side chain of Lasonolide A.

The key steps of the retrosynthesis are vinyl Grignard reaction, intramolecular Claisen rearrangement and the final coupling between **6** and (±) - **13**. The synthesis of allylic alcohol from 4-bromo-2-methyl-2-butene and diethyl

malonate was done in three steps in an overall yield of 67% (Scheme 1). The methylene double bond in **6** was generated using NaH (60%) to form sodium salt of the enolate anion under reflux condition⁴ and then subsequent reduction by using LAH at r.t.

Scheme 1. Reagents : (a) K₂CO₃, Bu₄Ni, DMF, r.t., 48 h (33%), (b) H₂/Pd-C, EtOH, r.t., (52%), (c) NaH (60%), DME, reflux, LAH at r.t., (67%).

The pyranoid ring of the second fragment was constructed from pentane-1,5-diol (Scheme 2). Pentane-1,5-diol (**7**) was converted to protected ester (**8**) which was further

Scheme 2. Reagents : (a) (i) DHP/DCM, PTSA, 0°C, r.t., (44%), (ii) PDC, DCM, r.t. 4 h (81%), (iii) PPh₃=CH-CO₂Et, dry benzene, reflux (70%), (b) (i) Cat, HCl, MeOH, r.t., (64%), (ii) Cat. NaH/THF (-78°C), (60%), (c) (i) LiAlH₄, ether, 0°C (68%), (ii) PDC, DCM, 4 h, r.t., 80%, (d) CH₂=CH-MgBr, THF, 0°C (65%), (e) BnO-CH₂-CO₂H, DMAP, DCC, r.t., (59%).

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deprotected and cyclised using catalytic amount of NaH (60%)⁵ afforded **6**. LAH reduction, PDC oxidation, vinyl Grignard reaction and corresponding esterification gave (**12**), which is an important synthon for 3,3-sigmatropic ester enolate intramolecular Claisen rearrangement. The details had been given in the experimental part.

Compound **12** was treated with of LiHMDS (3 eq., 1 M in THF, prepared *in situ* by standard procedure (experimental details are given in the next part) in THF at -78°C for 2 h. Then freshly distilled TMSCl (3 eq.) was added to it. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to r.t., then kept for 1 h at r.t. (Scheme 3). Then, dist. MeOH (3 ml), 5% NaOH (5 ml) were added to it and finally it was acidified with dil. HCl and extracted with ethyl acetate. The residue afforded was chromatographed using ethylacetate-pet. ether (8 : 2) as eluant which gave 2-benzyloxy-6-tetrahydro-2H-2-pyranyl-4-hexenoic acid as a syrup (15 mg, 49%) **13** (\pm). In case of **13**, there were two distinct multiplets, one at δ 3.98–4.10 and the other at δ 4.10–4.20 which indicated that **13** is a mixture of two diastereomers (\pm). From the integration of the proton at the chiral center, it is obvious that the ratio of two diastereomers was 3.5 : 1 (under dry Grignard condition), but they are inseparable even by chiral HPLC. The IR spectrum (neat) \sim 3394 cm^{-1} (C-CO₂H). Compound was analysed as C₁₈H₂₄O₄ CIMS (m/z , rel. intensity) 305 (60) [$M^+ + 1$].

Scheme 3

According to Fujisawa⁶, due to the chelation of the lithium metal with the 2-oxygen atom, the OBn moiety will occupy a downward position, thus giving fixed enolate geometry which resulted in the stereoselectivity of Claisen rearrangement to form **13a** as the major product.

Compound **13** (\pm) was coupled with **6** in presence of DCC, DMAP⁷ at r.t., under N₂ atm. for 24 h to yield **14** (\pm) which was chromatographed using ethyl acetate-pet. ether (4 : 96) as eluant to afford a colourless oil (11 mg, 53%). The diastereomers of **14** (\pm) were partially resolved by chiral HPLC (chiralcel OD column) using 10% *n*-isopropanol in

hexane at flow rate of 1 ml/min (UV = 225 nm) to afford **14a** (4.2 mg, 40%, de 61.64%, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +6.69$ (*c*, 0.62, CHCl₃). The ¹H NMR of **14a** clearly showed the separate two distinguishable multiplet signals at δ 3.15–3.3 (1H) and 3.34–3.51 (1H) for H₃ protons, which implies the fact at H₃ is attached to a chiral center C₂ (which resembled the C₂₈ of side chain of Lasonolide A). Moreover the H₂ proton together with the protons adjacent to oxygen atom to THP ring appeared as a multiplet at δ 4.00–4.15. The final compound showed a molecular ion (+1) peak at m/z (rel. intensity) 415 (11.9) in the mass spectrum and analysed for C₂₆H₃₈O₄ as $M^+ = 414$ which confirms the structure of **14a**, the north west portion (towards the C₂₃-C₃₅ side chain) of Lasonolide A.

Scheme 4. Reagents : (a) DCC, DMAP, N₂, 24 h, 53%. (b) chiral HPLC, 40%.

The above protocol is certainly useful to get the absolute stereochemistry of **14a**, since the pyran unit is going to be a carbohydrate derivative and the newly generated allylic hydroxyl center at C₂₈ in **1**, can be obtained by sharpless epoxidation followed by reductive opening of the epoxide. As the Claisen rearrangement retains the chirality at the rearranged product our strategy is certainly useful to obtain the required unit (C₂₈-C₃₅) in optically pure form. The synthesis of the top and bottom half (C₇-C₁₆ and C₁₈-C₂₃) fragments had already been achieved by our group and work is currently under progress towards the total synthesis.

Experimental

5-Methyl-2-vinyl-hex-1-ol (**6**) :

Diethyl 2-isopentylmalonate (2 g, 9.565 mmol) ion dimethoxy ethane (DME, 18 ml) was added dropwise during 2 h to a stirred mixture of prewashed sodium hydride (50%) suspension (0.478 g, 11.95 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h, cooled to 0°C and LAH (0.101 g, 2.668 mmol) was added in portions during 20 min to the reaction mixture. It was allowed to stir at room temperature for 12 h, cooled to 0°C and ether (50 ml), water (10 ml) and aq. NaH (5%, 10 ml) added sequentially. The separated solid was filtered and washed with water. The combine ether layer

was washed with brine, dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent removed and residue distilled under reduced pressure gave **6** as a colourless oil yield was 67%. ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 0.90 (6H, d, J 6.82 Hz, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.00–1.70 (3H, m, H_5 , H_4), 2.035 (2H, t, J 9.09 Hz, H_3), 4.03 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-OH}$), 4.85 (1H, s, olefin proton), 4.98 (1H, s, olefin proton). IR (neat, cm^{-1}) 3400 (OH), 2923, 1456 CIMS (m/z , rel. intensity): M^+ 128 (32) FAB HRMS: Calculated for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$: M^+ 128.1201; found 128.1202. Analytical calculation for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$: C, 75.06; H, 12.60; found: C, 75.04; H, 12.58, $\text{M}^+=128$.

1-Tetrahydro-2H-2-pyranylmethyl allyl-2-benzyloxy acetate (12):

To a stirred solution of 2-benzyloxy acetic acid (0.45 g, 2.71 mmol) and DMAP (0.1313 g, 1.0748 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (cooled to 0°C), dropwise 1-tetrahydro-2H-2-pyranyl-3-buten-2-ol (**2**) (0.335 g, 2.15 mmol) in dry dichloromethane was added, followed by a solution of dicyclocarbodiimide (DCC, 0.556 g, 2.694 mmol) in dry dichloromethane through cannula under N_2 . The reaction mixture was stirred at 0°C for 30 min, warmed to room temperature and stirred for 24 h till white ppt. appeared. The white ppt. was removed by filtration through a small pad by silica (SiO_2) and the pad was washed with chloroform. The filtrate was concentrated in vacuo and the compound was purified by column chromatography using (5 : 95) ethyl acetate : pet-ether solvent mixture as eluent. Yield was 59%.

^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.40–1.90 (8H, m,

, 3.99–4.09 (2H, d, J 4.54 Hz, $-\text{O}-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_2-\text{OBn}$), 4.60 (2H, d, J 2.72 Hz, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 5.10–5.34 (2H, m, H_4), 5.45–5.60 (1H, m, H_2), 5.67–5.89 (1H, m, H_3), 7.29 (5H, s, C_6H_5). IR (neat, cm^{-1}) 2930 (CH str, vib, olefinic), 1750 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ str, vib), 1035 (O-C-C ester), 1120 (C-CO-O bond of sat ester). Analytical calculation for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$: C, 71.11; H, 7.96, found C, 71.09; H, 7.94, $\text{M}^+ = 304$.

2-Benzyloxy-6-tetrahydro-2H-2-pyranyl-4-hexenoic acid: The preparation of this compound has been mentioned in the text part. ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.410–

1.65 (4H, m, , 3.98–4.10 (7/9H, m, H_2

major), 4.10–4.20 (2/9H, m, H_2 minor), 4.55–4.75 (2H, ABq, J 11.2 Hz, benzylic CH_2), 5.40–5.70 (2H, m, H_4 , H_5), 7.25–7.45 (m, aromatic protons).

2-2'-Isopentylallyl-5'-methyl-2-benzyloxy-6-tetrahydro-2H-2-pyranyl-4-hexenoate (14a) or ($\text{C}_{23}\text{-C}_{35}$) side chain of Lasonolide A:

The details of the experiment had been mentioned in the text part [α] $_D^{20} = +6.49$ (CHCl_3 , 0.62), ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 0.80–0.99 (6H, m, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.45–1.90 (3H, m, 5'H, 4'H), 1.90–2.40 (2H, m, H_6), 2.45–2.58 (2H, m, 3'H), 3.15–3.30 (1H, m, H_3), 3.34–3.51 (1H, m, H_3), 4.00–4.15 (5H, m, H_2 , , 5.36 (1H, q, J 3.57 Hz, H_5 (fractional)), 5.53 (2H, q, J 7.14 Hz, H_4 major, H_5 minor), 7.30 (5H, m, aromatic protons). CIMS (m/z , rel. intensity) ($\text{M}^+ + 1$) = 415 (11.9). Analytical calculation for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_4$: C, 75.43; H, 9.25, found: C, 75.41; H, 9.24, $\text{M}^+ = 414$. ^{13}C NMR: since the final compound **14a** was very less (~1 mg), and our 200 MHz NMR was not so susceptible to detect the ^{13}C peaks in that small concentration, so it was not possible to take the ^{13}C NMR. Thus the final confirmation of the **14a** was done by CIMS and analytical calculation.

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